

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC FINANCE IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract

Until the 20th century, there were no stable long-term forms of financial institutions in the Muslim world that could be defined as “banks”. The first banks, in their classical form, owned by Muslims (the corporate “majority”) began to appear after the 1920s. The collapse of the colonial system after the Second World War led to the emergence of new states, including Muslim ones. These states needed their own financial systems - this is how the first national banking institutions of Muslim countries began to appear.

Since the second half of the XX century, in the Muslim world, primarily in the Middle East, a process begins, called “Islamic revival” - a term that refers to various types of spread or strengthening of Islam. An important role in this was played by the religious concept - *tajdīd*, which manifested itself throughout the history of Islam in periodic calls for the restoration of basic religious principles in public relations. Much of the “Islamic revival” of the second half of the 20th century was driven by disillusionment with the secular national powers and pro-Western ruling elites that had dominated the Muslim world for previous decades and who increasingly showed signs of authoritarian, ineffective political systems and lacking cultural authenticity.

Keywords: Islamic economics, analysis, history, *tajdīd*

In scholarly literature, “Islamic revival” is an umbrella term covering a wide variety of movements, both intolerant and insular and pluralistic; both committed to science and anti-scientific; both predominantly religious and predominantly political; both democratic and authoritarian; both peaceful and warlike” [10].

It was in the wake of the Islamic revival that various reformist political movements began to be created and legislative reforms based on Sharia began to be carried out. In turn, the academic environment offered its ideas and concepts regarding new organizational forms of doing business, which would be consistent with religious requirements. Thus, significant works devoted to this subject were made: Said Gilani (1947), Muhammad Uzair (1955), Abdullah al-Araby (1967), Nejatullah Siddiqi (1961, 1969), al-Najjar (1971), Baqir al-Sadr (1961, 1974).

In the middle of the twentieth century, certain financial institutions were already functioning, reminiscent of Islamic banking. In the late 1950s, a financial institution operated in the rural areas of Pakistan, which issued microcredits to local residents without charging interest [11].

In 1963, the first modern Islamic bank, Mit Ghamr Savings Bank, was officially founded in the Egypt (Mit Ghamri). The pioneer was the economist Dr. Ahmad Elnaggar. The business model consisted of using the savings of the population for issuing loans based on the joint participation of depositors in the income of the institution.

In 1968, the experiment was closed by the government, but many rated it as a success [2].

Around the same time (1963) in Malaysia, the Pilgrims Saving Corporation was founded by the Malaysian government, the main goals of which were: a) to help Muslims save funds to cover the costs (transport, insurance, etc.) for the Hajj; b) enable Muslims to invest their savings in a manner that is consistent with religious requirements (*halal*). And although at the beginning of its activity, Pilgrims Saving Corporation was not a bank, in the literal sense, but it fully functioned on the basis of the concept of Islamic banking, while investing in low-risk assets - real estate, government securities. Over time (in 1969), this financial institution evolved into a full-fledged Pilgrims Management and Fund Board investment fund, now known as Tabung Hajj [2].

It was these two financial institutions - Mit Ghamr Savings and Pilgrims Saving Corporation, whose business model was based on the mechanism of activity of European savings banks - the classic German Sparkasse (from German, *sparen* - to save and *kasse* - cash desk) were the pioneers of the Islamic finance industry, and their relative commercial success has given rise to a variety of Islamic financial services and instruments.

Since the 1970s, the governments of Muslim countries have been involved in the process of creating the Islamic finance industry, their role has become proactive. A number of high-level international conferences are held, for example, the Conference of Islamic Finance Ministers (Karachi, 1970), a large-scale study of the potential of Islamic institutions at the level of the Egyptian government (1972), the First International Conference on Islamic Economics (Mecca, 1976), International Economic Conference (London, 1977). The result of such meetings is the creation of an institutional

architecture for regulating the industry.

A significant impetus for the further spread of the Islamic banking sector in these years was provided by the influx of “petrodollars” into the Persian Gulf countries and the general trend of “re-Islamization” after the Yom Kippur War and the 1973 oil crisis. One of the consequences of the 1973 oil crisis (also known as the “oil embargo”) was a threefold increase in the price of oil - from \$3 to \$12 per barrel, which allowed exporting countries to make super profits. It was thanks to them that the creation of two international financial groups was financed, which formed the core of Islamic banking - Dar al-Mal al-Islami Group (1981, Bahrain) and Al-Bakara Group (1982, Saudi Arabia), with an authorized capital of \$ 1 billion. [13].

During the 1980s, there were conflicting trends in the Islamic finance industry. On the one hand, it increased its expansion by offering deposits to Muslims with “great benefits” and “religious guarantees”. Islamic jurists were attracted for support, who actively issued fatwas (theological and legal conclusions) condemning traditional financial institutions and encouraging their Islamic counterparts. There were first cases of the introduction of a system of state regulation, for example, the government of Pakistan in 1980 adopted a regulatory framework for a large part of Islamic instruments. On the other hand, some secular Muslim political regimes, concerned about the rise of Islamist movements (which relied, among other things, on financial independence), launched media campaigns against Islamic banks. For example, the actions of the Egyptian government of Gamal Nasser in 1988 caused a banking panic and led to the bankruptcy of some Islamic financial institutions [2].

By the beginning of the 1990s Islamic banks were widely spread in the market in order to attract the attention of government agencies and institutions interested in introducing innovative products. In 1999, the Dow Jones Islamic Market Index (DJIMI) was introduced in Bahrain. DJIMI was the first index created for investors who prefer investments in accordance with Islamic law. The DJIMI calculation is based on the methodology of the Dow Jones Industrial Average, with the only difference that DJIMI has two additional levels of selection of companies for listing:

- companies that do not engage in types of business prohibited by Islam (haram), including ordinary financial services, since there are interests, fixed income, derivatives, and the like;
- companies that meet the established standards of financial ratios regarding the debt burden, the share of interest income in their balance sheet.

The first Islamic commercial bank founded outside the Muslim world was established in London, in 2004 - Islamic Bank of Britain, and before that, in 1996, the American international bank - Citibank began to provide Islamic banking services in Bahrain, establishing Citi Islamic Investment Bank there [2].

At the beginning of the 21st century, Islamic finance is becoming the fastest growing segment of the global financial system. During the first years from the beginning of the century, until the global financial crisis of 2008, the Islamic financial industry grew at a rate

of 10-15% per year [14].

During the global financial crisis of 2008, not a single Islamic bank was declared bankrupt (due to the conservatism of the Islamic finance model and the outright prohibition of speculation and excessive risk). According to a study by Ernst & Young, even after the financial crisis, the growth of Islamic banking assets was faster than banking assets in general. For example, in 2009-2013 its growth rate was 17.6% [16]. However, the decline in the value of real estate and corporate paper, the two main segments of Islamic banks, had a negative impact on the state of the industry.

In 2010-2020, Islamic banks increased the operations of financial instruments that bring high incomes. In these years, about 95% of the world's Islamic banking assets in the accounts of commercial banks were located in nine countries (Qatar, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, the United Arab Emirates and Turkey) [17].

According to the IFSB, the total value of assets managed by organizations operating in accordance with Sharia requirements at the beginning of 2020 was \$2 190 billion, of which \$1 571,3 billion was in banking assets, \$530,4 billion in the sukuk market, \$61,5 billion - assets of Islamic investment funds, \$27,7 billion - Islamic insurance takaful [15]. At the same time, Islamic financial institutions operate in 75 countries of the world.

Today, Islamic finance segments are classified, measured and regulated according to the following types of business: commercial banking; trade finance; insurance; operations in the capital market; investment banking services; equity and venture capital transactions.

At the same time, the gradual expansion of Islamic financial services looked like this [1]:

- commercial banking – 1970s;
- project financing – 1980s;
- Islamic Asset Management – 1990s;
- Ijara (leasing) – 2000s;
- sukuk / capital market – 2005s;
- takaful (insurance) – 2010s;
- istisna, mukarada – 2015s.

Today, there are approximately 1,8 billion Muslims in the world, which is 24,0% of the total population (7,8 billion). Pew Research Center research shows that the vast majority of them are religiously conservative.

As with any religious group, Muslim customs vary according to many factors, including where they live, but they are universally united by the basic principles of faith and the practice of certain religious rituals. However, there is less unity in other areas.

It is clear that the main reason for the rapid growth is the low statistical base - a few decades ago, the industry was created literally from scratch. In addition, steadily high oil prices, providing the Middle Eastern countries with an influx of petrodollars, contributed to the accumulation of significant financial resources, which were actively invested, including in the establishment of new financial institutions of the industry. However, today the share of assets of the Islamic banking industry is still small, and is approximately 1,25% of the entire global banking system. According to a

study by Ernst & Young, Islamic banking accounts for only a small proportion of all Muslim banking assets. For example, in Saudi Arabia, the assets of Islamic banks account for barely half of all banking assets, in Indonesia, the country with the largest Muslim population in the world, Islamic banking today occupies less than 5% of the market.

Despite decades of rapid development, the main conceptual questions still remain without a clear answer: a) is the doctrine of Islamic finance competitive in general and b) is it capable of being formed as a self-sufficient link in the global financial space, with an effective mechanism for integrating external financial agents (or will it remain exclusively niche) phenomenon of a number of regional markets).

However, for now, the vast majority, both scientists and experts of international financial institutions, expect the further development of the Islamic finance industry, at least over the next few decades. The main factor behind this is the increase in the Muslim population in the world. Islam is the fastest growing religion in the world, according to the New Research Center's demographic survey. In terms of linear extrapolation of today's population growth dynamics, the growth of Muslims by 2050 will be 73,0%, while the growth of the entire world population is only 35,0%. This growth dynamics is determined by the characteristics of the demographic composition of the Muslim population. For example, in terms of age distribution, the Muslim religious group contains the highest percentage of the younger population – 34,0% (for comparison, 27,0% in the world as a whole), the female fertility rate also significantly exceeds the world average and is 3.1 versus 2.5 [13].

Among polls in Islamic countries, the majority (84,0%) support Islamic law as official law. However, in some other countries, especially in Eastern Europe and Central Asia, in particular Turkey (12,0%), Kazakhstan (10,0%) and Azerbaijan (8,0%), a relatively small share of the population speaks in favor of this [11]. However, these data indicate the existence of a target audience base for further expansion of the markets for Islamic financial products.

In many Muslim countries (other than the Gulf countries), a large proportion of the population is financially excluded – only 24% of citizens have a bank account and 7% have access to formal finance, compared to 44% and 9% respectively for the non-Muslim population [12]. Also, the principles of risk sharing and the direct link between credit and collateral mean that Islamic banking is well suited to finance SMEs (thereby promoting more inclusive growth), and sukuk has proven to be an effective tool for financing infrastructure projects, which can also support investment and growth.

The impetus for the emergence and development of the Islamic finance industry was a process called the "Islamic revival". To a large extent, the "Islamic revival" of the second half of the XX century was driven by disillusionment with the secular national powers and pro-Western ruling elites that had dominated the Muslim world for previous decades and who increasingly

showed signs of authoritarian, ineffective political systems and lacking cultural authenticity.

It was in the wake of the Islamic revival that various reformist political movements began to be created and legislative reforms based on Sharia began to be carried out. In turn, the academic environment offered its ideas and concepts regarding new organizational forms of doing business, which would be consistent with religious requirements.

Despite decades of rapid development, the main conceptual questions still remain without a clear answer: a) is the doctrine of Islamic finance competitive in general and b) is it capable of being formed as a self-sufficient link in the global financial space, with an effective mechanism for integrating external financial agents (or will it remain exclusively "niche" phenomenon of a number of regional markets). However, for the time being, the vast majority of both scientists and experts of international financial organizations expect the further development of the Islamic finance industry, at least over the next few decades.

Taking into account the given data, namely: a) the growth dynamics of the Muslim population in the world; b) features of the demographic composition of the Muslim population and c) the existence of a target audience base for further expansion of the markets for Islamic financial products, it can be argued that numerous forecasts regarding the further extensive growth of the Islamic finance industry over the coming decades, in our opinion, are quite objective.

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